

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

CO₂ burst as a measurement of soil microbial activity

A healthy agricultural soil is full of microbes. Most of their activity is related to decomposition, which cycles nutrients and releases carbon dioxide (CO₂). Monitoring the release of CO₂ during a drying-rewetting experiment can be a good measure of the overall biological activity and nitrogen availability.

In a CO₂-burst experiment a soil sample is dried and sieved to remove large chunks of organic material. The drying puts soil biology to a resting state and some microbes die, releasing their contents to the soil surfaces. When the soil sample is rewetted (to 50% water filled pore volume), the enzymes on the soil activate and react with organic molecules, releasing a flush of CO₂. At the same time, the dormant micro-organisms

activate and start decomposition of readily available organic material. Like in a desert after a rain, there is a huge burst of biological activity. In this case it lasts a few days. Capturing the CO₂ released during the burst (24-h, 48-h, or 72-h) can be a useful measure of the size of the microbial population and the availability and quality of food for microbes.

The CO₂ burst has been found to be a rapidly responding indicator for soil health, especially microbial activity. In addition, it correlates well with N mineralization from soil and can be used to fine-tune N fertilizer application rates. There are commercial kits available (Solvita), but the test kit can also be constructed from canning jars and a flow-through CO₂ sensor.

1. CO₂ production can be measured with a relatively simple DIY setup (container, flow through CO₂ meter and MicroBit - datalogger).

KEYWORDS

Microbial activity, monitoring, nitrogen mineralization

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